

Microplastics and Nanoplastics in the Gastrointestinal System: Mechanisms, Risks, and Therapeutic Opportunities

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Abstract:

Microplastics (MPs; <5 mm) and nanoplastics (NPs; <1000 nm) are pervasive environmental contaminants increasingly detected in food, water, and human biological samples. The gastrointestinal (GI) tract represents a primary site of exposure, yet the full scope of their impact on human health remains incompletely understood. This review synthesizes current evidence on the role of MPs and NPs in gastrointestinal disease, extending beyond microbiome disruption to include epithelial barrier dysfunction, immune activation, oxidative stress, and systemic effects.

Experimental and emerging clinical data suggest that MPs compromise intestinal integrity by disrupting tight junction proteins and inducing reactive oxygen species, leading to increased permeability and chronic inflammation. These mechanisms are implicated in the pathogenesis of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), colorectal cancer (CRC), irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), and other GI disorders. MPs also alter gut microbiota composition, promote dysbiosis, and interact with immune cells to drive pro-inflammatory signaling. Beyond the GI tract, MPs may contribute to systemic effects through the gut–brain axis and endocrine disruption.

In addition to mechanistic insights, this review highlights emerging strategies for mitigation and intervention, including probiotic-based approaches, enzyme-mediated degradation of plastics, targeted delivery systems such as lipid nanoparticles, and polysaccharide-based binding agents. Advances in detection technologies for environmental and biological samples are also discussed as critical tools for exposure assessment and risk stratification.

Together, these findings underscore the need for integrated approaches combining detection, prevention, and therapeutic intervention to address the growing burden of microplastic exposure and its implications for gastrointestinal and systemic health.

Keywords: Microplastics (MPs), Gastrointestinal (GI) diseases, Intestinal barrier dysfunction, Gut microbiome, Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), Oxidative stress

1. Introduction

Plastic has infiltrated every environment humans inhabit despite counterregulatory measures to prevent environmental pollution. There are said to be an estimate of 15 trillion and 51 trillion microplastic particles floating in surface waters worldwide¹. Unfortunately, only in the modern decades has science come to discover the deleterious effects plastic compounds have on human health. Microplastics (MP), plastic with particulate matter < 5mm in diameter, and nanoplastics, plastic with particulate matter <1000 nanometers, are the most notable offenders.

They infiltrate through an animal's innate immune defenses such as the skin and gastrointestinal (GI) tract to reach all organs of the body².

The three main ways MPs enter the body are via absorption through the GI tract, through the integumentary system, or via inhalation. However, it appears most MP particles in the body enter via oral feeding. While the mechanism of absorption is still unclear, studies in rats have shown that inflammation via the NF- κ B pathway and cell cytotoxicity leads to increased epithelial permeability permitting the transportation of plastic particles from lumen to circulation³.

In vitro models have been used in the field as well that show MP exposure induces chemical-induced damage to the epithelial lining that serves as a likely mechanism explaining MP-induced GI disease⁴. Worsening gut health may correlate to increased absorption of toxic microparticles from our environment, creating a dangerous cycle of increased gut leakiness, increased microparticle absorption, and a damaged intestinal epithelial tight junctions and gut barrier. The increasing prevalence of Inflammatory bowel disease and leaky gut in developed countries highlights the importance of uncovering the mechanism. More recently, research has elucidated the potential impact MPs have on the gut microbiome in numerous animal models, highlighting the importance for further research in humans to elucidate MPs' gastrointestinal impact fully⁵. The focus of this review will be to explore the broader impact of MPs on GI health, beyond just the microbiota, including connections to IBD, colorectal cancer, and other chronic health disorders.

Methods

This narrative review aims to synthesize the current literature on the intersection between plastics exposure—including microplastics—and gastrointestinal disease in human and experimental models. Relevant articles were identified through searches in PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus using search terms such as “microplastics,” “nanoplastics,” “intestinal inflammation,” “GI disease,” “gut microbiota,” and “gastrointestinal injury.” No restrictions were placed on study design, and both in vivo and in vitro studies were considered. Additional references were included through manual searches of bibliographies in key articles and related reviews to broaden the scope and capture emerging evidence.

Inclusion criteria encompassed articles published in English addressing either human or experimental animal/cellular models of plastics exposure with reported outcomes relevant to GI function, barrier integrity, inflammatory markers, or microbiota composition. Studies focusing specifically on extraction/quantification techniques for microplastics in biological tissues, mechanistic insights into plastics-GI interactions, and health outcomes following plastics exposure were prioritized. Exclusion criteria involved reviews lacking original data, articles not relevant to GI disease, and studies where plastics exposure was incidental rather than intentional.

2. Mechanisms of Microplastic Impact on the Gastrointestinal System

Microplastics and Intestinal Barrier Dysfunction

The intestinal epithelial lining serves as the primary barrier against external insults, maintaining a delicate balance between nutrient absorption and pathogen exclusion. MPs have been increasingly implicated in disrupting this protective layer, resulting in increased permeability, commonly referred to as leaky gut. MPs achieve this through multiple pathways, including direct mechanical abrasion, oxidative stress induction, and disruption of tight junction proteins⁶. Research has demonstrated that MPs interact with epithelial cells, causing lipid bilayer destabilization and tight junction disassembly, leading to an increase in paracellular

permeability. Zeng et al. exposed C57BL/6J mice to polystyrene microplastics (Polystyrene-MPs; 0.2, 1, and 5 μm) by oral gavage at 1 mg/kg/day for 28 days and showed size-dependent barrier injury; Polystyrene (PS)-5 μm caused the greatest decreases in ZO-1/occludin/cludin-1 and increased permeability⁷. Tight junction proteins such as occludin and claudins, critical in maintaining intestinal integrity, exhibit altered expression profiles in response to MP exposure. This weakening of the intestinal barrier allows for the translocation of harmful substances, including bacteria and environmental toxins, exacerbating gut inflammation and systemic immune activation⁸.

Oxidative stress is another major consequence of MP exposure in the GI tract. Studies have shown that MPs stimulate the excessive production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) within epithelial cells, leading to mitochondrial dysfunction and DNA damage. Persistent activation of these inflammatory cascades contributes to chronic gut inflammation, including inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and colorectal cancer⁹. In mice orally exposed to polypropylene MPs (PP-MPs), Jia et al. reported colonic apoptosis and tight-junction impairment via oxidative stress and TLR4/NF- κB signaling. The study contrasted 8 μm vs 70 μm PP-MPs and noted stronger inflammatory signaling with 8 μm particles; some experimental groups used suspensions up to ~10 mg/mL, a level higher than typical human dietary exposure—an important limitation for extrapolation⁹.

Figure 1. Microplastics and nanoplastics disrupt gastrointestinal homeostasis through multiple converging mechanisms.

Ingested particles interact with the intestinal epithelium, inducing oxidative stress and disrupting tight junction proteins, leading to increased intestinal permeability. Concurrently, microplastics promote immune activation, including macrophage polarization and pro-inflammatory cytokine release, and alter gut microbiota composition. These combined effects contribute to chronic inflammation and gastrointestinal disease pathogenesis.

Interaction with the Gut Immune System

Beyond structural damage to the gut lining, MPs have profound immunomodulatory effects that may contribute to chronic immune dysregulation. The immune cells within the gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT) serve as first responders to foreign particles, and exposure to MPs has been found to elicit significant alterations in immune function. Studies have revealed that MPs can be internalized by intestinal macrophages, leading to immune cell activation and the secretion of inflammatory mediators¹⁰. This was shown by Merkley et al. with murine macrophages that phagocytosed PS-MPs, then adopting an immunometabolic state characterized by a glycolytic shift, reduced mitochondrial respiration, and upregulation of activation markers (CD80/CD86) and cytokine genes—consistent with pro-inflammatory polarization. Most data derive from in-vitro systems and need confirmation in primary human cells¹⁰. One of the most concerning aspects of MP exposure is its potential role in promoting macrophage polarization towards a proinflammatory M1 phenotype¹⁰. M1 macrophages are known to: produce high levels of ROS and inflammatory cytokines, foster an environment of chronic inflammation and tissue damage, and impaired phagocytic activity of macrophages¹⁰.

Emerging evidence suggests that MPs may also play a role in the pathogenesis of autoimmune-like responses within the gut. The persistent stimulation of the immune system by MPs may lead to a loss of tolerance, causing aberrant immune activation against self-antigens¹¹. Collectively, these findings highlight the multifaceted ways in which MPs contribute to gastrointestinal dysfunction, spanning from physical barrier disruption to chronic immune system dysregulation.

3. Microplastics and Gut Microbiota

Alteration of Gut Microbiota Diversity

MP exposure has been increasingly recognized as a disruptor of gut microbial balance, leading to dysbiosis. Several animal studies have confirmed that MPs, including polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polystyrene, can alter both alpha diversity (within-sample diversity) and beta diversity (between-sample diversity) in the gut microbiome^{6,12}. For example, PET microplastics (PET MPs average particle size determined by image analysis at $160\ \mu\text{m} \pm 110\ \mu\text{m}$ with irregular morphology) altered human gut microbiota composition during simulated GI digestion, with signs of microbial community restructuring even in the absence of complete degradation of the polymer⁵. In rodent studies, these changes have been linked to reduced levels of beneficial bacteria like *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*, while promoting opportunistic pathogens such as *Escherichia coli* and *Clostridium spp.*⁶ This dysbiosis has critical implications for GI health through its role in the fermentation of dietary fibers, synthesis of vitamins (e.g, Vitamin K and B vitamins), and maintenance of mucosal immunity. Microplastics were noted to interfere with microbial metabolites like short-chain fatty acids which are essential for gut barrier function and immune regulation.¹² MPs may also act as vectors for toxic substances and environmental pollutants, introducing additional stress to the gut environment and compounding microbial imbalance.¹³ Over time, these changes could contribute to chronic GI disorders, metabolic dysfunction, and even systemic inflammatory conditions due to disrupted host-microbe interactions.

Links to Gastrointestinal Disease

Inflammatory Bowel Disease

Emerging research has drawn a compelling connection between MP exposure and the onset or exacerbation of IBD (i.e. Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis). Fecal samples from individuals with IBD have been found to contain significantly higher concentrations of microplastics compared to healthy controls, suggesting either increased ingestion or decreased excretion efficiency. Quantified fecal MPs and found higher counts in IBD vs controls (median 41.8 vs

28.0 items/g dry matter), with PET (22–34%) and polyamide (9–12%) dominant polymers. The cross-sectional design supports correlation—not causation—and results may be affected by sampling and analytical contamination risks; standardized digestion and spectroscopic confirmation are needed¹¹. Furthermore, animal models mimicking IBD-like conditions have shown that exposure to MPs worsens disease severity, including increased epithelial damage, elevated pro-inflammatory cytokine expression, and more extensive mucosal ulceration.⁶ These findings suggest that MPs may not only serve as irritants but also modulate immune responses by altering the gut microbiota or directly interacting with immune cells via pathways such as Toll-like receptor activation¹⁴. These multifaceted interactions underscore the potential role of MPs in the development and progression of IBD.

Colorectal Cancer

Chronic dysbiosis and continuous low-grade inflammation induced by MPs may contribute to colorectal cancer development by creating a pro-tumorigenic environment¹³. Continuous immune activation, oxidative stress, and gut barrier dysfunction can facilitate DNA damage and cellular transformation in the colonic epithelium¹⁵. Additionally, some MPs possess the potential to adsorb and deliver carcinogenic substances such as polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and heavy metals, increasing localized oxidative stress and DNA damage in intestinal epithelial cells⁵. Recent epidemiological evidence shows a correlation between microplastic exposure and the rising incidence of early-onset colorectal cancer, particularly in individuals under 50 years old⁴. Thus, long-term MP exposure presents a plausible environmental risk factor for colorectal cancer development, warranting further epidemiological and mechanistic investigation.

4. Microplastics and Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD)

IBD Pathogenesis and Microplastic Exposure

Recent studies have established a significant association between microplastic concentrations in human feces and IBD. A study analyzing fecal samples found that IBD patients had markedly higher MP concentrations (41.8 items/g dry matter) compared to healthy individuals (28.0 items/g dry matter), with a positive correlation between MP levels and IBD severity. The predominant MP types detected were polyethylene terephthalate and polyamide, commonly originating from plastic packaging and environmental dust.¹⁶ These findings suggest that MP exposure may contribute to IBD pathogenesis or that IBD may impair the clearance of MPs.

Mechanistically, MPs can exacerbate IBD by inducing oxidative stress and disrupting the intestinal barrier. . In murine models, exposure to polystyrene microplastics led to increased ROS production and activation of the NF- κ B/NLRP3/IL-1 β /MLCK signaling pathway (PS-MPs 0.2–5 μ m; 1 mg/kg/day; 28 days), resulting in inflammation and compromised gut barrier integrity¹⁷. However, doses and particle burdens in preclinical studies are often higher than estimated human intakes, limiting direct translation.⁷ Furthermore, exposure to polyethylene MPs has been shown to disrupt the balance between intestinal stem cell self-renewal and differentiation, leading to colonic epithelial homeostasis imbalance and increased susceptibility to colitis.¹⁷ These insights underscore the potential role of MPs in aggravating IBD through oxidative and inflammatory mechanisms.

Inflammation and Gut Permeability

Compromised gut permeability and chronic inflammation are central features of IBD and MPs have been shown to exacerbate these conditions. MP exposure can impair the intestinal barrier by reducing mucus secretion and downregulating tight junction proteins such as ZO-1, occludin,

and claudin-1, leading to increased intestinal permeability.⁷ This barrier dysfunction facilitates the translocation of luminal antigens, triggering immune responses and sustaining inflammation.

Additionally, MPs can stimulate the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, further amplifying the inflammatory milieu.¹⁸ These cytokines not only perpetuate intestinal inflammation but also contribute to systemic immune activation. Moreover, MPs have been implicated in altering gut microbiota composition, promoting dysbiosis, which is associated with IBD progression.^{18,19} Collectively, these findings highlight the multifaceted ways in which MPs can intensify gut inflammation and permeability, thereby influencing IBD pathogenesis.

5. Gastrointestinal Diseases Beyond IBD

Colorectal Cancer

Chronic GI inflammation is a well-established risk factor for colorectal cancer (CRC), with persistent inflammatory processes promoting tumor initiation and progression. Emerging evidence suggests that MP exposure may exacerbate these inflammatory pathways, thereby contributing to CRC development. A recent study demonstrated that MPs are present in human CRC tissues and can increase CRC incidence in animal models. The study found that MP exposure promoted tumor progression and oxaliplatin chemoresistance via mTOR/ULK1-linked protective autophagy. Although mechanistically compelling, many regimens use bolus or elevated MP burdens; human exposure-equivalent dosing and tissue quantification are priority gaps²⁰. Additionally, MPs have been shown to disrupt gut microbiota composition, leading to dysbiosis and increased intestinal inflammation, which are key factors in CRC pathogenesis²¹.

Other GI Disorders

Irritable Bowel Syndrome (IBS) is characterized by abdominal discomfort and altered bowel habits, with gut microbiota imbalance playing a significant role in its pathophysiology. Studies have indicated that MP exposure can lead to intestinal dysbiosis, marked by an increase in pathogenic bacteria and a decrease in beneficial microbial populations²¹. This microbial imbalance can disrupt gut barrier function and promote low-grade inflammation, potentially exacerbating IBS symptoms. Furthermore, MPs have been shown to increase intestinal permeability and stimulate the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines, such as IL-1 β and TNF- α , which may contribute to the symptomatology of IBS¹⁹. Peptic ulcers and gastric mucosal damage are affected by mucosal injury from MPs, which can lead to ulcer formation²¹.

Moreover, MPs can facilitate the colonization of *Helicobacter pylori*, a known risk factor for peptic ulcers, by providing surfaces for biofilm formation and enhancing bacterial adhesion to the gastric mucosa²².

6. Systemic Impacts of Microplastics via the Gut Gut-Brain Axis and Neurodegenerative Diseases

The gut-brain axis is a bidirectional communication network connecting the gastrointestinal tract and the central nervous system, playing a crucial role in maintaining neurological health.

Emerging evidence suggests that MPs can disrupt this axis, potentially contributing to neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's. MPs induce gut inflammation and alter the gut microbiome, leading to dysbiosis. This gut dysbiosis can trigger neuroinflammation through immune activation and the release of inflammatory mediators,

thereby affecting brain function. Studies have demonstrated that MPs can translocate from the gut to systemic circulation, reaching the brain and potentially exacerbating neurodegenerative processes. The presence of MPs in brain tissues has been associated with increased neuroinflammation and neuronal damage, highlighting the potential risk of MPs in neurodegenerative disease pathogenesis¹⁵. Reviews of nanoplastic/MP note that CNS delivery is often demonstrated with fluorescent 1–2 µm polystyrene particles at bolus doses enabling detection. These designs support plausibility but may overestimate real-world uptake^{13,15}.

Endocrine Disruption:

MPs are known to leak endocrine-disrupting chemicals (EDCs), such as bisphenol A (BPA) and phthalates, which can interfere with hormonal balance. These EDCs can mimic or inhibit natural hormones, leading to disruptions in endocrine function. Exposure to EDCs from MPs has been linked to metabolic disorders, including obesity and diabetes²³. Studies have shown that EDCs can alter the function of endocrine organs, such as the thyroid and adrenal glands, and affect reproductive health. While endocrine-active plasticizers (e.g., BPA, phthalates) can leach from plastics, robust human biomonitoring directly linking MP-bound EDCs to endocrine outcomes remains limited. Still, the widespread presence of MPs in the environment raises concerns about their potential role in the increasing prevalence of metabolic and endocrine disorders²⁴.

Understanding the systemic impacts of microplastics via the gut is essential for developing strategies to mitigate their potential health risks. Further research is needed to elucidate the mechanisms by which MPs influence the gut-brain axis and endocrine system, and to assess the long-term consequences of chronic exposure to MPs. Epidemiologic associations exist for persistent organic pollutants and metabolic disease and broader obesogen literature, but MP-specific dose–response data in humans are sparse^{23,24}.

7. Potential Therapeutic Approaches and Mitigation Strategies

7.1 Probiotic and Prebiotic Interventions

Emerging research suggests probiotics may help restore gut microbiota disrupted by MPs and reduce related inflammation. *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei* DT66 and *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum* DT88 have been identified as effective strains, reducing polystyrene particles in mice by over 60% through co-aggregation and enhancing excretion²⁵. *L. plantarum* DT88 also lowered pro-inflammatory cytokines (IL-6, TNF-α) and increased anti-inflammatory IL-10^{25,26}. MPs disrupt gut microbiota diversity and promote harmful biofilms, but probiotics can rebalance microbes, strengthen the intestinal barrier, and boost short-chain fatty acids^{5,25,26}. Probiotics could reduce MP adhesion to gut tissues, improve excretion, and ease inflammation^{25,26}.

However, more standardized models are needed to simulate real-world MP exposure, including particle type and co-contaminants^{5,25}. Overall, probiotics show promise in mitigating the harmful effects of MPs on gut health, but more research is needed to understand the most effective strains, dosages, and treatment strategies.

Figure 2. Emerging therapeutic strategies targeting microplastic and nanoplastic burden in the gastrointestinal system.

Proposed interventions include engineered probiotics capable of enzymatic degradation, direct enzyme-based approaches, targeted delivery systems such as lipid nanoparticles, and polysaccharide-based binding agents that facilitate aggregation and excretion. These strategies aim to reduce particle burden, restore gut barrier integrity, and mitigate inflammation.

7.2 Detection Methods

Scalable detection methods for microplastics in environmental and biological matrices could enable early assessment of exposure and associated health risks. Novel approaches include high-throughput assays for detecting microplastics in tap water, oceans, and bodily fluids like blood and urine, potentially using enzyme-based or fluorescence-based techniques to quantify polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polystyrene (PS) particles. Such methods could identify at-risk populations, linking microplastic levels to gastrointestinal diseases (e.g., IBD, colorectal cancer) and systemic effects (e.g., gut-brain axis disruption). Preliminary studies suggest these assays are feasible in preclinical models, with ongoing research exploring their application in human samples (unpublished data). By facilitating real-time monitoring, these detection strategies could inform targeted interventions and public health policies to reduce microplastic exposure. Further development is needed to standardize assays for clinical and environmental use, ensuring reproducibility across diverse matrices. Combined with regulatory measures and filtration technologies, scalable detection offers a critical tool for mitigating microplastic-related health risks, aligning with the principle that early detection enables protective interventions.

Measurement in tissues remains technically challenging: FTIR and Raman spectroscopy differ in lower size detection limits (often $\sim 1\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$ depending on instrumentation), require rigorous contamination control, and can misclassify particles without polymer-specific signatures. Current heterogeneity limits cross-study comparison and reliable body-burden estimates^{6,8}.

7.3 Treatment and Therapeutic Approaches

Novel therapeutic approaches could mitigate microplastic-induced gastrointestinal damage and associated diseases like inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) and colorectal cancer (CRC) as

demonstrated in **Figure 2**. Specialized probiotics engineered to express enzymes like PETase could degrade polyethylene terephthalate (PET) into non-toxic monomers, potentially reducing inflammation and microbial dysbiosis in the gut (Lin et al., 2025). Lipid nanoparticles (LNPs) designed to deliver PETase or anti-inflammatory compounds, such as curcumin, to the colon offer another promising strategy, enhancing targeted therapy for microplastic accumulation.

Nutraceuticals like chlorella and mucilaginous polysaccharides (e.g., okra, marshmallow root) could bind microplastics and support gut barrier function, with preliminary evidence suggesting reduced inflammation in preclinical models (Zheng et al., 2024). These integrative strategies, supported by ongoing research, highlight the potential to address microplastic-related health risks through combined microbial, nanotechnological, and dietary interventions. Clinical validation is needed to confirm efficacy and safety in humans, alongside continued exploration of complementary approaches like improved filtration and regulatory bans to reduce exposure.

8. Future Directions and Research Gaps

Despite growing evidence linking MP exposure to GI disorders such as IBD and colorectal cancer, key knowledge gaps remain. Future research should focus on large-scale human studies to establish causal links, as most existing data come from animal and in vitro models. Understanding the exact mechanisms of MP absorption and their interactions with gut microbiota is critical, particularly in relation to oxidative stress, immune activation, and epithelial damage. Additionally, dose-response studies are needed to determine safe exposure thresholds.

Regulatory measures are still in their early stages, with agencies like the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) working to address microplastic contamination. However, current policies lack clear exposure limits for MPs in food and water. Strengthening filtration standards in water treatment plants, enforcing extended producer responsibility (EPR) programs, and banning hazardous plastic additives like bisphenol A are essential steps to mitigate health risks.

On an individual level, reducing reliance on plastic-packaged foods, filtering drinking water, and choosing biodegradable alternatives can help minimize MP exposure. Consumer advocacy and increased public awareness are also vital in pressuring industries and policymakers to take action. As microplastic contamination continues to rise, a multi-faceted approach involving research, regulation, and personal precautions will be crucial in addressing its impact on human health.

Figure 3. Conceptual framework linking environmental exposure to clinical outcomes and intervention strategies.

Microplastics and nanoplastics originate from environmental sources and enter the human body primarily through ingestion. These particles contribute to gastrointestinal dysfunction and systemic effects through multiple biological pathways. Integrated approaches, including environmental monitoring, diagnostic assessment, and targeted therapeutics, are needed to address exposure and downstream health impacts.

9. Conclusion

Microplastics represent a pervasive and increasingly recognized threat to gastrointestinal health, with mounting evidence linking their presence to epithelial damage, immune dysregulation, microbial dysbiosis, and chronic inflammation. While early research focused on their impact on gut microbiota, it is now clear that MPs contribute more broadly to the pathogenesis of diseases such as inflammatory bowel disease, colorectal cancer, irritable bowel syndrome, and even systemic conditions through disruption of the gut-brain axis and endocrine signaling. These findings underscore the importance of expanding our understanding of MPs' multifactorial mechanisms of action, including their ability to act as vectors for toxicants and their influence on both local and systemic inflammation.

From a public health standpoint, the growing evidence on microplastic exposure calls for immediate attention. Regulatory agencies must establish clearer guidelines on acceptable levels of microplastics in food, water, and consumer goods. While some progress has been made in banning microbeads, broader action is needed to address microplastics in packaging, processed foods, and drinking water. Public health departments can support this by encouraging testing in high-risk areas and developing clear communication strategies to educate communities.

Infrastructure improvements like enhanced water filtration and better waste management systems can reduce the amount of microplastics entering the environment. On a personal level, individuals can take simple steps—such as using water filters, choosing glass or stainless-steel containers, and avoiding plastic-packaged foods—to reduce their exposure. Schools, hospitals, and public institutions can also lead by example by minimizing plastic use in their procurement policies.

Finally, increased collaboration between scientists, healthcare professionals, and policymakers will be essential to translate emerging research into effective prevention strategies. By combining education, policy, and innovation, we can better protect population health from the long-term risks of microplastic exposure.

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